

COMMUNICATION THROUGH PLAYING IN CHILDREN WITH AUTISM

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Abstract. *In this article, games with children with autism syndrome and pedagogical methods of communication through games are highlighted.*

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Autism (from the Greek word "autos" - "myself") is a specific state of the psyche, in which the patient does not want to communicate with the outside world and people around him. He likes solitude. He repeats the same behavior and words. The disease term "autism" was introduced to science in 1912 by E. Bleiler. According to him, a sick person lives in his own world. His thinking is not like that of others. Their actions are not related to reality. Emotional experiences play a key role in patients' actions. This syndrome is more common in boys than in girls. The variety of symptoms and the variability of the disease indicate the difficulty of this disease: from subtle autistic features to the need for constant care. As the main symptoms of autism, the child's inability to relate to others with looks, facial expressions, gestures, stereotypes of behavior is manifested in the congenital inability. Children with autism syndrome have specific characteristics such as a tendency to constant repetitive behavior, excessive and unusual exposure to various objects, and resistance to changes in the environment. Autistic children respond to different things in their own way. For example, they react angrily to an unfavorable environment. In such children, there is a delay in the development of speech, which is not related to the level of intellectual development. Autism manifests very early, mostly before the thirtieth month of life.

Autism symptoms are clearly observed at the age of 3-5 years, and such symptoms are characterized by fear, aggression, negativism. Later, disorders in intellectual and personal development appear.

Games encouraging speech communication

The first step to wanting to communicate is to master gestures. The exchange of gestures or words helps the child to feel close to his relatives, to consider himself a participant in the relationship, to agree and manage this relationship. The child gradually begins to appreciate communication not only as a way to get candy or a kiss, but because communication itself is as pleasant as candy or a kiss. Imagine yourself at a dinner party with a loved one who understands you well, who looks you in the eye when you speak and listens intently. It's not that he understands and approves of your every word, but that you feel a deep sense of closeness, belonging, and appreciation. A four-month-old baby feels the same way when he laughs at his mother, and her mother laughs back with joy. If a child values communication, it automatically leads him to use words and become a "talking machine" - talking non-stop, telling you about everything in the world: "Hey, look at this," "Daddy, look what I did," and so on. In normal children, this stage usually occurs between the ages of two and four. Many parents even wish the child would talk

less: "Wait a minute. I'm talking to your grandmother on the phone." Children with autistic spectrum disorders often have this stage later, but when we were able to help them, they enjoyed the acquired words so much that they also wanted to tell us all about what they did. When communication brings pleasure, children tend to imitate adults and learn words quickly. If children learn communication only through imitation, the process will be slower. With speech motor problems, a child may not be able to pronounce certain sounds, but he will certainly try to make some sounds, perhaps replacing them with others. It is not at all alarming if the child speaks his own language in the beginning, when you are working on his speech motor skills, if you have learned to understand what he is trying to say. A child can play games that practice pronouncing different sounds and learn to say words as they are. Sometimes children start by babbling and using words that seem random at first. If you can help your child think, you can help him learn to understand. If a little girl suddenly says "car" without any meaning, show her a toy car and her favorite doll and see which toy she gravitates towards. Intonate the words that indicate the toys he wants and doesn't want, for example: "Do you play with dolls or cars?" He'll probably say, "The doll," and go after it with a laugh, or shake his head at the car, or, if you're lucky, say, "No car." In this way, you will help the child to use the word consciously, not mechanically. In order to give meaning to the words, it is very important to achieve emotional interaction, in our example, the child really wanted a doll, not a car.

Relying on the child's interests in play and communication

A child learns role-play when you involve him in a joint action using imagination. When you feed a doll, it feeds its doll; the doll reaches out and says to the other doll: "Give me one more hug." As time passes, events develop and the dolls hug each other, feed each other, etc. k. will happen. The main thing is that the child will have to take the initiative. Role-playing games help create a world filled with different symbols and increase a child's ability to use words and concepts. Usually, during role-play, children simply repeat what they see at home at first - this is normal. But from the very beginning, they can introduce the fruits of their imagination. At first, they feed the doll, just like its mother, but then the doll suddenly pushes away the food and says: "No." says His parents wonder where it came from. This will come from the child's imagination. To interest the child, you need to prepare carefully; it is useful to stock up toy copies of household items so that the child can play plots based on life experience; it is then that the imagination can be activated for the first time. Dolls and stuffed animals can act as family members or friends of the baby. The child also needs life experience in the outside world - nature, walks, supermarkets, interactive children's museums, subway rides, games played in the sand. To find out what the child prefers to play at home, this experience can be activated in the child's memory by using objects at hand.

Using role-playing games in communication

Incorporate imaginative elements into activities your child enjoys to extend role play. For example, if he is playing with kitchen tools, imagine him as a chef (and you can be a chef's assistant). Start by playing a plot familiar to the child. Then encourage him to show his imagination, for this you will have to do a trick: if the child's doll kisses your doll, your doll will run away and may say, "Your doll must find me for a kiss." Suddenly, a boring game becomes exciting, a child's doll will look for yours and catch it. In the meantime, continue to introduce new words, inviting the child to respond verbally and creatively to you. The main thing is to make gestures and speak on behalf of your character (it can be a doll, a puppy or a mare that you are depicting on all fours, etc.). We have developed an affect-based language acquisition course for

systematic teaching of speech. Its main feature is to create a world of symbols, strengthen the connection between new words and their meanings with the help of role-playing games (also emotional) that fill the child's inner world with meaningful symbols, a real experience enriched with the child's emotions. . Over time, the child's imagination develops: spaceships go to the moon, ballerinas impress the audience, or sea creatures scare everyone. In role-playing games, adults should share the child's interest in the world of imagination. For example, if the child is interested in the car, then check if he carries the doll. But speak for the doll, not for yourself. Become a puppet and show the child how to enter the imaginary world. It introduces him to new ideas and symbolic devices. On behalf of the doll, "May I ride in your car?" May I? If you don't mind, I'll get in your car. Then put the doll in the child's car and he can turn the doll. Then introduce another puppet as a policeman and say on his behalf: "Where are you going? To your grandmother's house or to school?" and point to the two boxes. A child may not even know what grandma's house or school is, but that's how he learns. He simply points to one of the two houses and says, "Uh-huh." You: "Is that right? - you ask, - but this is your grandmother's house. It is even possible to place a photo of the grandmother at the edge of the playground so that the child can associate the proposed idea with the image of the grandmother. For children with impaired motor or sensory information processing, it is difficult to imagine the world and therefore play role-playing games. . For children with auditory information processing disorders, it is sometimes necessary to break down instructions into simple, easy-to-repeat small sentences. But it is not necessary to speak too slowly and monotonously, keep a normal rhythm and intonation so that the child learns to respond to the meaning of your emotional speech. It is difficult for children with impaired processing of visual information to remember the images of objects, and therefore it is not easy for them to play role-playing games. If such a child moves quickly from one toy to another, help him connect the images of the toys by explaining their role once again. For such a child, it is better to collect them in easy-to-see groups so that the toys are not scattered everywhere. should be helped to play and play out their ideas to the end. Turn such activities into performances with a fixed sequence, like singing or dancing: include their texts and bows, clapping, etc. How to take into account the child's interests? Children who need emotions and are always on the move will not be able to sit still and play with their dolls. Parents often ask, "What should I do if my child does not want to play with dolls?" In such cases, parents themselves can be toys. For example, the father says: "I am a lion and I am going to your house." Parents can introduce themselves as their child's favorite characters from books, movies, or TV shows, play dress-up with the child, or develop a story by exchanging sounds and words.

Parents often complain that they are running out of ideas and can't think of what the doll should say. If you feel like you're at a dead end, just watch the child for a few seconds and ask yourself what would be fun for him: is he trying to climb on the sofa or playing with one doll and another? do i I have often seen parents, for example, trying to teach a child to hug a doll, and the child runs towards the door. Adults: "Stop, don't go. "Go back and play with your doll," they say, and the child becomes nervous. Remember that your goal is to teach him to use ideas, not to master a specific role-playing game. A child can be taught to think and speak by standing in front of the door, sitting on the couch, or playing with dolls together. If the child wants to go on the couch, then it is interesting for him. Ask him, "Would you like to play with your doll on the couch?" If the child points to the sofa, ask him: "Can you get under the pillow or go up?" After a while, the boy said: "Up!" - learns to speak. Continue the dialogue: "Okay, we'll go to the couch. What about

a doll? He will be very upset! Shall we leave it on the floor or take it with us?' The child probably looks at the doll. If he doesn't look, pick him up and he'll start to get out of your couch, and you'll repeat, "Get out, get out, too!" Then pass the doll to the child and ask "Where will the doll go now?" - you can ask. If the child grabs the doll and throws it on the floor, this can be turned into a game. The main principle is to go with the flow, but not follow the child's path. His plans may include wordless play, self-motivated or aimless actions, and endless repetition of the same plot. To avoid this, you need to create another plot line, revive the game with new twists. Introduce a conflict or task for the child to solve, and use his negative reaction to complicate the plot. The origin of the conflict helps the child to add new ideas to the game. Conflicts should be created when the child starts to act unexpectedly or is distracted. But don't try to change the plot of the game itself. It is even possible to emphasize the determination of the child ("It will be okay! All the dolls are walking in the same step, commander!"). Don't be afraid of negative behavior by introducing conflict. You are helping the child to develop and become more intelligent. If the child is interested and continuously interacting with you using more and more ideas and words, he may be using aimless actions or himself. -definitely gets more pleasure from this exercise than self-stimulation. The most important thing is to create favorable conditions for his studies. Adhering to these principles, slowly and carefully introduce complex and unpleasant sensations for the child - sounds, sensations, motor development exercises through role-playing games. (Be sure to go back to the sensory experiences your child loves to help him calm down when he's upset or upset). giving a teddy bear) is not necessary, it is better to wait for him to express his desire with words or gestures, sometimes for this it is useful to pretend that you do not understand what he wants. When you force a child to express his wishes with words or gestures, you help him to convey information with symbols, and not to get stuck in it by using only what he knows in the "here and now". Thus, he goes from reacting automatically in the same pattern to thinking, and this is the time when a dramatic change in his development takes place.

Based on the Floortime methodology, it is effective at the initial stages, when the tasks of attracting attention, establishing a relationship, providing a continuous flow of goal-oriented communication and emotional gestures, and encouraging the use of ideas are ahead. Such games, which take into account the characteristics of the child's nervous system, facilitate his introduction to the world and help him start using various ideas.

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